

Table 1.

Demographic characteristics of eligible children (n=38,554).

	Birth number		
	First (N=18,144)	Second (N=14,379)	Third (N=6,031)
Characteristics of children			
Sex, n(%)*			
Boys	9,357(51.6)	7,330(51.0)	3,157(52.3)
Girls	8,787(48.4)	7,049(49.0)	2,874(47.7)
Singleton or multiple birth, n(%) *			
Singleton birth	17,952(98.9)	14,064(97.8)	5,815(96.4)
Multiple birth	192(1.1)	315(2.2)	216(3.6)
Term or preterm birth, n(%) *			
Term birth	17,233(95.0)	13,614(94.7)	5,609(93.0)
preterm birth	911(5.0)	765(5.3)	422(7.0)
Day care attendance, n(%) ‡			
Not attend	11,555(63.7)	9,045(62.9)	3,502(58.1)
Attend	4,155(22.9)	3,504(24.4)	1,586(26.3)
Missing	2,434(13.4)	1,830(12.7)	943(15.6)
Parental characteristics			
Maternal age at delivery, n(%) *			
< 25	2,684(14.8)	955(6.6)	139(2.3)
25~29	6,221(34.3)	3,607(25.1)	1,058(17.5)
30~34	5,983(33.0)	5,925(41.2)	2,307(38.3)
35~	3,256(17.9)	3,892(27.1)	2,527(41.9)
Maternal smoking status, n(%) †			
Non-smoker	17,107(94.3)	13,350(92.8)	5,300(87.9)
Smoker(≤10)	785(4.3)	747(5.2)	504(8.4)
Smoker(>10)	203(1.1)	241(1.7)	207(3.4)
Missing	49(0.3)	41(0.3)	20(0.3)
Maternal educational attainment, n(%) ‡			
University or higher	4,835(26.6)	3,131(21.8)	822(13.6)
Junior college or vocational school	6,280(34.6)	5,373(37.4)	2,034(33.7)
High school	3,887(21.4)	3,454(24.0)	1,777(29.5)
Junior high school and others	671(3.7)	573(4.0)	440(7.3)
Missing	2,471(13.6)	1,848(12.9)	958(15.9)
Paternal educational attainment, n (%) ‡			
University or higher	7,324(40.4)	5,394(37.5)	1,672(27.7)
Junior college or vocational school	2,814(15.5)	2,274(15.8)	909(15.1)
High school	4,258(23.5)	3,913(27.2)	1,882(31.2)
Junior high school and others	927(5.1)	815(5.7)	520(8.6)
Missing	2,821(15.5)	1,983(13.8)	1,048(17.4)
Residential place of living, n(%) * §			
Wards	5,692(31.4)	3,915(27.2)	1,401(23.2)
Cities	11,158(61.5)	9,262(64.4)	3,986(66.1)
Towns or Villages	1,294(7.1)	1,202(8.4)	644(10.7)

* Obtained from the birth record.

† Obtained from the first survey(at the age of 6 months).

‡ Obtained from the second survey(at the age of 18 months).

§ The population scale varies greatly by region, but as a general, cities typically have a population of 50,000 or more (up to 10 million or more in major metropolitan areas), wards range from 100,000 to 1 million, and towns and villages have populations below 50,000.

Table 2.

Distributions of the birth number, separated by included or loss to follow-up at each survey.

	Included in the analysis	Lost to follow-up
2nd survey (at 18 months)	32,035(83.1)	6,519(16.9)
First	15,058(83.0)	3,086(17.0)
Second	12,113(84.2)	2,266(15.8)
Third	4,864(80.6)	1,167(19.4)
3rd survey (at 30 months)	30,946(80.1)	7,608(19.7)
First	14,508(80.0)	3,636(20.0)
Second	11,743(81.7)	2,636(18.3)
Third	4,695(77.8)	1,336(22.2)
4th survey (at 42 months)	28,173(73.1)	10,381(26.9)
First	13,197(72.7)	4,947(27.3)
Second	10,769(74.9)	3,610(25.1)
Third	4,207(69.8)	1,824(30.2)
5th survey (at 54 months)	26,591(69.0)	11,963(31.0)
First	12,568(69.3)	5,576(30.7)
Second	10,150(70.6)	4,229(29.4)
Third	3,873(64.2)	2,158(35.8)
6th survey (at 66 months)	26,529(68.8)	12,025(31.2)
First	12,593(69.4)	5,551(30.6)
Second	10,072(70.0)	4,307(30.0)
Third	3,864(64.1)	2,167(35.9)
7th survey (at 7 years)	24,466(63.5)	14,088(36.5)
First	11,670(64.3)	6,474(35.7)
Second	93,60(65.1)	5,019(34.9)
Third	3,436(57.0)	2,595(43.0)
8th survey (at 8 years)	23,749(61.6)	14,805(38.4)
First	11,350(62.6)	6,797(37.4)
Second	9,070(63.1)	5,309(36.9)
Third	3,329(55.2)	2,702(44.8)
9th survey (at 9 years)	23,456(60.8)	15,098(39.2)
First	11,205(61.8)	6,939(38.2)
Second	8,949(62.2)	5,430(37.8)
Third	3,302(54.8)	2,729(45.2)

Table 3.

Demographic characteristics, separated by included or loss to follow-up at 2nd survey.

	Included in the analysis (N=32,035)	Lost to follow-up (N=6,519)
Characteristics of children		
Birth number, n (%) *		
First	15,058(47.0)	3,086(47.3)
Second	12,113(37.8)	2,266(34.8)
Third	4,864(15.2)	1,167(17.9)
Sex, n(%)*		
Boys	16,540(51.6)	3,304(50.7)
Girls	15,495(48.4)	3,215(49.3)
Singleton or multiple birth, n(%) *		
Singleton birth	31,453(98.2)	6,378(97.8)
Multiple Birth	582(1.8)	141(2.2)
Term or preterm birth, n(%) *		
Term birth	30,347(94.7)	6,109(93.7)
preterm birth	1,688(5.3)	410(6.3)
Day care attendance, n(%) ‡		
Not attend	22,972(71.7)	1,130(17.3)
Attend	9,054(28.3)	191(2.9)
Missing	9(0)	5,198(79.7)
Parental characteristics		
Maternal age at delivery, n(%) *		
< 25	2,573(8.0)	1,205(18.5)
25~29	8,823(27.5)	2,063(31.6)
30~34	12,250(38.2)	1,965(30.1)
35~	8,389(26.2)	1,286(19.7)
Maternal smoking status, n(%) †		
Non-smoker	30,170(94.2)	5,587(85.7)
Smoker(≤ 10)	1,383(4.3)	653(10.0)
Smoker(> 10)	407(1.3)	244(3.7)
Missing	75(0.2)	35(0.5)
Maternal educational attainment, n(%) ‡		
University or higher	8,554(26.7)	234(3.6)
Junior college or vocational school	13,230(41.3)	457(7.0)
High school	8,635(27.0)	483(7.4)
Junior high school and others	1,551(4.8)	133(2.0)
Missing	65(0.2)	5,212(80.0)
Residential place of living, n(%) * §		
Ward	9,227(28.8)	1,781(27.3)
City	20,260(63.2)	4,146(63.6)
Town or Village	2,548(8.0)	592(9.1)

* Obtained from the birth record.

† Obtained from the first survey(at the age of 6 months).

‡ Obtained from the second survey(at the age of 18 months).

§ The population scale varies greatly by region, but as a general, cities typically have a population of 50,000 or more (up to 10 million or more in major metropolitan areas), wards range from 100,000 to 1 million, and towns and villages have populations below 50,000.

Table 4.

Crude and adjusted* RRs for associations between birth order and bronchial asthma from 6 months to 9 years of age.

	Ncase/N	% of cases	Crude RRs (95% CI)	Adjusted* RRs (95% CI)	Adjusted* RRs (95% CI)
Between 6 and 18 months (n=32,035)					
First	351/1,5058	2.33	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	
Second	516/12,113	4.26	1.83(1.60-2.09)	1.97(1.71-2.26)	
Third	273/4,864	5.61	2.41(2.06-2.81)	2.65(2.23-3.13)	
Between 18 and 30 months (n=30,946)					
First	603/14,508	4.16	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	
Second	710/11,743	6.05	1.45(1.31-1.62)	1.53(1.36-1.71)	
Third	295/4,695	6.28	1.51(1.32-1.73)	1.60(1.38-1.86)	
Between 30 and 42 months (n=28,173)					
First	700/13,197	5.30	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	
Second	718/10,769	6.67	1.26(1.14-1.39)	1.29(1.16-1.44)	
Third	293/4,207	6.96	1.31(1.15-1.50)	1.37(1.19-1.59)	
Between 42 and 54 months (n=26,591)					
First	858/12,568	6.83	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	
Second	712/10,150	7.01	1.03(0.93-1.13)	1.02(0.93-1.13)	
Third	286/3,873	7.38	1.08(0.95-1.23)	1.06(0.92-1.22)	
Between 54 and 66 months (n=26,529)					
First	904/12,593	7.18	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	
Second	689/10,072	6.84	0.95(0.87-1.05)	0.94(0.85-1.04)	
Third	261/3,864	6.75	0.94(0.82-1.07)	0.91(0.79-1.05)	
Between 66 months and 7years (n=24,466)					
First	635/11,670	5.44	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	
Second	519/9,360	5.54	1.02(0.91-1.14)	1.02(0.90-1.15)	
Third	166/3,436	4.83	0.89(0.75-1.05)	0.86(0.72-1.03)	
Between 7 and 8 years (n=23,749)					
First	542/11,350	4.78	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	
Second	405/9,070	4.47	0.94(0.82-1.06)	0.94(0.82-1.07)	
Third	123/3,329	3.69	0.77(0.64-0.94)	0.73(0.60-0.90)	
Between 8 and 9 years (n=23,456)					
First	492/11,205	4.39	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	
Second	408/8,949	4.56	1.04(0.91-1.18)	1.06(0.93-1.22)	
Third	120/3,302	3.63	0.83(0.68-1.01)	0.80(0.65-0.99)	

CI, confidence interval; RR, risk ratio.

* Adjusted for child factors (sex, singleton or multiple birth, term or preterm birth), parental factors (maternal age at delivery, maternal smoking status, maternal educational attainment, and paternal educational attainment), and residential place of living.

* p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001, the p-values compared to the first is provided from a test of multiplicative interaction.

Table 5.

Crude and adjusted* RRs for associations between birth order and food allergy from 6 months to 9 years of age.

	Ncase/N	% of cases	Crude RRs (95% CI)	Adjusted* RRs (95% CI)	Adjusted* RRs (95% CI)
Between 6 and 18 months (n=32,035)					
First	1,047/15,058	6.95	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	
Second	646/12,113	5.33	0.77(0.70-0.84)	0.76(0.69-0.84)	0.76(0.69-0.84)
Third	187/4,864	3.84	0.55(0.47-0.64)	0.58(0.49-0.68)	0.58(0.49-0.68)
Between 18 and 30 months (n=30,946)					
First	607/14,508	4.18	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	
Second	416/11,743	3.54	0.85(0.75-0.96)	0.84(0.74-0.96)	0.84(0.74-0.96)
Third	133/4,695	2.83	0.68(0.56-0.81)	0.74(0.61-0.91)	0.74(0.61-0.91)
Between 30 and 42 months (n=28,173)					
First	403/13,197	3.05	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	
Second	283/10,769	2.63	0.86(0.74-1.00)	0.86(0.72-0.99)	0.86(0.72-0.99)
Third	80/4,207	1.90	0.62(0.49-0.79)	0.66(0.51-0.84)	0.66(0.51-0.84)
Between 42 and 54 months (n=26,591)					
First	280/12,568	2.23	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	
Second	215/10,150	2.12	0.95(0.8-1.13)	0.91(0.76-1.10)	0.91(0.76-1.10)
Third	55/3,873	1.42	0.64(0.48-0.85)	0.68(0.50-0.92)	0.68(0.50-0.92)
Between 54 and 66 months (n=26,529)					
First	196/12,593	1.56	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	
Second	143/10,072	1.42	0.91(0.74-1.13)	0.86(0.69-1.07)	0.86(0.69-1.07)
Third	41/3,864	1.06	0.68(0.49-0.95)	0.66(0.46-0.94)	0.66(0.46-0.94)
Between 66 months and 7years (n=24,466)					
First	216/11,670	1.85	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	
Second	172/9,360	1.84	0.99(0.81-1.21)	0.99(0.77-1.16)	0.99(0.77-1.16)
Third	44/3,436	1.28	0.69(0.50-0.95)	0.69(0.46-0.92)	0.69(0.46-0.92)
Between 7 and 8 years (n=23,749)					
First	168/11,350	1.48	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	
Second	130/9,070	1.43	0.97(0.77-1.22)	0.91(0.72-1.15)	0.91(0.72-1.15)
Third	30/3,329	0.90	0.61(0.41-0.90)	0.55(0.37-0.83)	0.55(0.37-0.83)
Between 8 and 9 years (n=23,456)					
First	173/11,205	1.54	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	
Second	128/8,949	1.43	0.93(0.74-1.16)	0.92(0.73-1.16)	0.92(0.73-1.16)
Third	30/3,302	0.91	0.59(0.40-0.87)	0.51(0.34-0.79)	0.51(0.34-0.79)

CI, confidence interval; RR, risk ratio.

* Adjusted for child factors (sex, singleton or multiple birth, term or preterm birth), parental factors (maternal age at delivery, maternal smoking status, maternal educational attainment, and paternal educational attainment), and residential place of living.

* p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001, the p-values compared to the first is provided from a test of multiplicative interaction.

Table 6.

Crude and adjusted* RRs for associations between birth order and atopic dermatitis from 6 months to 9 years of age.

	Ncase/N	% of cases	Crude RRs (95% CI)	Adjusted* RRs (95% CI)	Adjusted* RRs (95% CI)
Between 6 and 18 months (n=32,035)					
First	555/15,058	3.69	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	
Second	468/12,113	3.86	1.05(0.93-1.18)	1.10(0.97-1.24)	
Third	186/4,864	3.82	1.04(0.88-1.22)	1.14(0.96-1.36)	
Between 18 and 30 months (n=30,946)					
First	600/14,508	4.14	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	
Second	569/11,743	4.85	1.17(1.05-1.31)	1.2(1.07-1.36)	**
Third	241/4,695	5.13	1.24(1.07-1.44)	1.35(1.15-1.59)	***
Between 30 and 42 months (n=28,173)					
First	603/13,197	4.57	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	
Second	585/10,769	5.43	1.19(1.06-1.33)	1.23(1.09-1.38)	**
Third	245/4,207	5.82	1.27(1.1-1.47)	1.39(1.19-1.63)	***
Between 42 and 54 months (n=26,591)					
First	672/12,568	5.35	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	
Second	623/10,150	6.14	1.15(1.03-1.28)	1.18(1.06-1.32)	**
Third	237/3,873	6.12	1.14(0.99-1.32)	1.23(1.05-1.43)	*
Between 54 and 66 months (n=26,529)					
First	611/12,593	4.85	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	
Second	559/10,072	5.55	1.14(1.02-1.28)	1.18(1.05-1.33)	**
Third	222/3,864	5.75	1.18(1.02-1.37)	1.29(1.09-1.51)	**
Between 66 months and 7years (n=24,466)					
First	700/11,670	6.00	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	
Second	603/9,360	6.44	1.07(0.97-1.19)	1.12(1.00-1.25)	*
Third	210/3,436	6.11	1.02(0.88-1.18)	1.10(0.94-1.29)	
Between 7 and 8 years (n=23,749)					
First	693/11,350	6.11	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	
Second	606/9,070	6.68	1.09(0.98-1.22)	1.14(1.02-1.28)	*
Third	198/3,329	5.95	0.97(0.84-1.14)	1.03(0.87-1.22)	
Between 8 and 9 years (n=23,456)					
First	670/11,205	5.98	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	
Second	574/8,949	6.41	1.07(0.96-1.19)	1.10(0.98-1.23)	
Third	211/3,302	6.39	1.07(0.92-1.24)	1.12(0.95-1.32)	

CI, confidence interval; RR, risk ratio.

* Adjusted for child factors (sex, singleton or multiple birth, term or preterm birth), parental factors (maternal age at delivery, maternal smoking status, maternal educational attainment, and paternal educational attainment), and residential place of living.

* p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001, the p-values compared to the first is provided from a test of multiplicative interaction.

Table 7.

Crude and adjusted* RRs for the association between different birth order and bronchial asthma stratified by sex.

male	Ncase/N	% of cases	Crude RRs (95% CI)	Adjusted* RRs (95% CI)	female	Ncase/N	% of cases	Crude RRs (95% CI)	Adjusted* RRs (95% CI)
Between 6 and 18 months (n=16,540)					Between 6 and 18 months (n=15,495)				
First	241/7,815	3.08	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	110/7,243	1.52	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	336/6,194	5.42	1.76(1.5-2.07)	1.90(1.60-2.25)	Second	180/5,919	3.04	2.00(1.58-2.53)	2.12(1.66-2.71)
Third	170/2,531	6.72	2.18(1.8-2.64)	2.42(1.96-2.98)	Third	103/2,333	4.41	2.91(2.23-3.79)	3.18(2.38-4.25)
Between 18 and 30 months (n=15,954)					Between 18 and 30 months (n=14,992)				
First	372/7,505	4.96	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	231/7,003	3.30	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	458/6,016	7.61	1.54(1.35-1.75)	1.63(1.41-1.87)	Second	252/5,727	4.40	1.33(1.12-1.59)	1.37(1.13-1.65)
Third	185/2,433	7.60	1.53(1.29-1.82)	1.64(1.36-1.99)	Third	110/2,262	4.86	1.47(1.18-1.18)	1.55(1.21-1.99)
Between 30 and 42 months (n=14,577)					Between 30 and 42 months (n=13,596)				
First	439/6,866	6.39	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	261/6,331	4.12	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	445/5,520	8.06	1.26(1.11-1.43)	1.31(1.15-1.50)	Second	273/5,249	5.20	1.26(1.07-1.49)	1.26(1.06-1.5)
Third	174/2,191	7.94	1.24(1.05-1.47)	1.31(1.09-1.58)	Third	119/2,016	5.90	1.43(1.16-1.77)	1.48(1.17-1.86)
Between 42 and 54 months (n=13,804)					Between 42 and 54 months (n=12,787)				
First	498/6,551	7.60	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	360/6,017	5.98	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	426/5,226	8.15	1.07(0.95-1.21)	1.05(0.92-1.19)	Second	286/4,924	5.81	0.97(0.84-1.13)	0.99(0.84-1.16)
Third	171/2,027	8.44	1.11(0.94-1.31)	1.09(0.91-1.31)	Third	115/1,846	6.23	1.04(0.85-1.28)	1.01(0.81-1.26)
Between 54 and 66 months (n=13,724)					Between 54 and 66 months (n=12,805)				
First	517/6,529	7.92	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	387/6,064	6.38	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	433/5,168	8.38	1.06(0.94-1.20)	1.05(0.93-1.20)	Second	256/4,904	5.22	0.82(0.70-0.95)	0.79(0.67-0.93)
Third	164/2,027	8.09	1.02(0.86-1.21)	1.01(0.84-1.21)	Third	97/1,837	5.28	0.83(0.67-1.03)	0.78(0.62-0.99)
Between 66 months and 7years (n=12,628)					Between 66 months and 7years (n=11,838)				
First	393/6,065	6.48	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	242/5,605	4.32	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	320/4,796	6.67	1.03(0.89-1.19)	1.02(0.88-1.19)	Second	199/4,564	4.36	1.01(0.84-1.21)	1.01(0.84-1.23)
Third	101/1,767	5.72	0.88(0.71-1.09)	0.86(0.69-1.08)	Third	65/16,69	3.89	0.90(0.69-1.18)	0.86(0.64-1.15)
Between 7 and 8 years (n=12,237)					Between 7 and 8 years (n=11,512)				
First	336/5,871	5.72	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	206/5,479	3.76	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	267/4,633	5.76	1.01(0.86-1.18)	1.00(0.85-1.18)	Second	138/4,437	3.11	0.83(0.67-1.02)	0.84(0.67-1.05)
Third	83/1,733	4.79	0.84(0.66-1.06)	0.81(0.63-1.05)	Third	40/1,596	2.51	0.67(0.48-0.93)	0.62(0.43-0.88)
Between 8 and 9 years (n=12,061)					Between 8 and 9 years (n=11,395)				
First	300/5,810	5.16	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	192/5,395	3.56	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	267/4,562	5.85	1.13(0.97-1.33)	1.15(0.97-1.36)	Second	141/4,387	3.21	0.90(0.73-1.12)	0.93(0.75-1.17)
Third	70/1,689	4.14	0.80(0.62-1.04)	0.76(0.58-1.00)	Third	50/1,613	3.10	0.87(0.64-1.18)	0.87(0.63-1.22)

CI, confidence interval; RR, risk ratio.

* Adjusted for child factors(sex, singleton or multiple birth, term or preterm birth), parental factors(maternal age at delivery, maternal smoking status, maternal educational attainment, and paternal educational attainment), and residential place of living.

Figure 1.

Adjusted* RRs for the association between different birth order and bronchial asthma stratified by sex.

A male

* Adjusted for child factors (sex, singleton or multiple birth, term or preterm birth), parental factors (maternal age at delivery, maternal smoking status, maternal educational attainment, and paternal educational attainment), and residential place of living.

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, the p-values compared to the first is provided from a test of multiplicative interaction.

Table 8.

Crude and adjusted* RRs for the association between different birth order and food allergy stratified by sex.

male	Ncase/N	% of cases	Crude RRs (95% CI)	Adjusted* RRs (95% CI)	female	Ncase/N	% of cases	Crude RRs (95% CI)	Adjusted* RRs (95% CI)
Between 6 and 18 months (n=16,540)					Between 6 and 18 months (n=15,495)				
First	599/7,815	7.66	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	448/7,243	6.19	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	375/6,194	6.05	0.79(0.70-0.89)	0.79(0.69-0.90)	Second	271/5,919	4.58	0.74(0.64-0.86)	0.72(0.62-0.84)
Third	110/2,531	4.35	0.57(0.47-0.69)	0.59(0.48-0.73)	Third	77/2,333	3.30	0.53(0.42-0.68)	0.56(0.43-0.71)
Between 18 and 30 months (n=15,954)					Between 18 and 30 months (n=14,992)				
First	354/7,505	4.72	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	253/7,003	3.61	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	248/6,016	4.12	0.87(0.75-1.02)	0.86(0.73-1.02)	Second	168/5,727	2.93	0.81(0.67-0.98)	0.81(0.66-0.99)
Third	76/2,433	3.12	0.66(0.52-0.84)	0.70(0.54-0.92)	Third	57/2,262	2.52	0.70(0.52-0.93)	0.81(0.59-1.09)
Between 30 and 42 months (n=14,577)					Between 30 and 42 months (n=13,596)				
First	232/6,866	3.38	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	171/6,331	2.70	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	166/5,520	3.01	0.89(0.73-1.08)	0.89(0.72-1.10)	Second	117/5,249	2.23	0.83(0.65-1.04)	0.78(0.61-1.00)
Third	47/2,191	2.15	0.63(0.47-0.87)	0.67(0.48-0.93)	Third	33/2,016	1.64	0.61(0.42-0.88)	0.63(0.42-0.92)
Between 42 and 54 months (n=13,804)					Between 42 and 54 months (n=12,787)				
First	158/6,551	2.41	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	122/6,017	2.03	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	128/5,226	2.45	1.02(0.81-1.28)	0.99(0.78-1.27)	Second	87/4,924	1.77	0.87(0.66-1.14)	0.80(0.60-1.07)
Third	30/2,027	1.48	0.61(0.42-0.90)	0.63(0.42-0.96)	Third	25/1,846	1.35	0.67(0.44-1.02)	0.74(0.47-1.16)
Between 54 and 66 months (n=13,724)					Between 54 and 66 months (n=12,805)				
First	114/6,529	1.75	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	82/6,064	1.35	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	80/5,168	1.55	0.89(0.67-1.18)	0.81(0.60-1.10)	Second	63/4,904	1.28	0.95(0.69-1.32)	0.91(0.65-1.27)
Third	29/2,027	1.43	0.82(0.55-1.23)	0.80(0.51-1.24)	Third	12/1,837	0.65	0.48(0.26-0.88)	0.45(0.24-0.85)
Between 66 months and 7years (n=12,628)					Between 66 months and 7years (n=11,838)				
First	125/6,065	2.06	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	91/5,605	1.62	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	89/4,796	1.86	0.90(0.69-1.18)	0.83(0.63-1.10)	Second	83/4,564	1.82	1.12(0.83-1.50)	1.09(0.80-1.48)
Third	24/1,767	1.36	0.66(0.43-1.02)	0.63(0.40-1.00)	Third	20/1,669	1.20	0.74(0.46-1.19)	0.69(0.41-1.16)
Between 7 and 8 years (n=12,237)					Between 7 and 8 years (n=11,512)				
First	92/5,871	1.57	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	76/5,479	1.39	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	74/4,633	1.60	1.02(0.75-1.38)	0.97(0.71-1.32)	Second	56/4,437	1.26	0.91(0.65-1.28)	0.85(0.59-1.20)
Third	19/1,733	1.10	0.70(0.43-1.14)	0.67(0.40-1.13)	Third	11/1,596	0.69	0.50(0.26-0.93)	0.42(0.21-0.82)
Between 8 and 9 years (n=12,061)					Between 8 and 9 years (n=11,395)				
First	101/5,810	1.74	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	72/5,395	1.33	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	73/4,562	1.60	0.92(0.68-1.24)	0.93(0.68-1.27)	Second	55/4,387	1.25	0.94(0.66-1.33)	0.92(0.64-1.31)
Third	16/1,689	0.95	0.54(0.32-0.92)	0.50(0.28-0.89)	Third	14/1,613	0.87	0.65(0.37-1.15)	0.54(0.29-1.01)

CI, confidence interval; RR, risk ratio.

* Adjusted for child factors(sex, singleton or multiple birth, term or preterm birth), parental factors(maternal age at delivery, maternal smoking status, maternal educational attainment, and paternal educational attainment), and residential place of living.

Figure 2.

Adjusted* RRs for the association between different birth order and food allergy stratified by sex.

A male

B female

* Adjusted for child factors (sex, singleton or multiple birth, term or preterm birth), parental factors (maternal age at delivery, maternal smoking status, maternal educational attainment, and paternal educational attainment), and residential place of living.

* p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001, the p-values compared to the first is provided from a test of multiplicative interaction.

Table 9.

Crude and adjusted* RRs for the association between different birth order and atopic dermatitis stratified by sex.

male	Ncase/N	% of cases	Crude RRs (95% CI)	Adjusted* RRs (95% CI)	female	Ncase/N	% of cases	Crude RRs (95% CI)	Adjusted* RRs (95% CI)
Between 6 and 18 months (n=16,540)					Between 6 and 18 months (n=15,495)				
First	346/7,815	4.43	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	209/7,243	2.89	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	269/6,194	4.34	0.98(0.84-1.15)	1.01(0.86-1.18)	Second	199/5,919	3.36	1.17(0.96-1.41)	1.24(1.02-1.51)
Third	107/2,531	4.23	0.95(0.78-1.18)	1.02(0.81-1.27)	Third	79/2,333	3.39	1.17(0.91-1.51)	1.35(1.03-1.78)
Between 18 and 30 months (n=15,954)					Between 18 and 30 months (n=14,992)				
First	347/7,505	4.62	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	253/7,003	3.61	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	314/6,016	5.22	1.13(0.97-1.31)	1.15(0.98-1.35)	Second	255/5,727	4.45	1.23(1.04-1.46)	1.27(1.06-1.52)
Third	139/2,433	5.71	1.24(1.02-1.50)	1.31(1.06-1.61)	Third	102/2,262	4.51	1.25(1.00-1.56)	1.41(1.10-1.80)
Between 30 and 42 months (n=14,577)					Between 30 and 42 months (n=13,596)				
First	336/6,866	4.89	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	267/6,331	4.22	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	304/5,520	5.51	1.13(0.97-1.31)	1.15(0.98-1.35)	Second	281/5,249	5.35	1.27(1.08-1.49)	1.31(1.11-1.55)
Third	133/2,191	6.07	1.24(1.02-1.51)	1.36(1.09-1.68)	Third	112/2,016	5.56	1.32(1.06-1.63)	1.42(1.12-1.79)
Between 42 and 54 months (n=13,804)					Between 42 and 54 months (n=12,787)				
First	372/6,551	5.68	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	300/6,017	4.99	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	330/5,226	6.31	1.11(0.96-1.28)	1.13(0.97-1.32)	Second	293/4,924	5.95	1.19(1.02-1.40)	1.24(1.05-1.46)
Third	122/2,027	6.02	1.06(0.87-1.29)	1.13(0.91-1.40)	Third	115/1,846	6.23	1.25(1.01-1.54)	1.34(1.07-1.68)
Between 54 and 66 months (n=13,724)					Between 54 and 66 months (n=12,805)				
First	344/6,529	5.27	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	267/6,064	4.40	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	302/5,168	5.84	1.11(0.95-1.29)	1.14(0.97-1.34)	Second	257/4,904	5.24	1.19(1.01-1.41)	1.22(1.03-1.46)
Third	120/2,027	5.92	1.12(0.92-1.37)	1.25(1.01-1.56)	Third	102/1,837	5.55	1.26(1.01-1.57)	1.32(1.04-1.67)
Between 66 months and 7years (n=12,628)					Between 66 months and 7years (n=11,838)				
First	384/6,065	6.33	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	316/5,605	5.64	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	306/4,796	6.38	1.01(0.87-1.17)	1.05(0.90-1.22)	Second	297/4,564	6.51	1.15(0.99-1.35)	1.2(1.02-1.40)
Third	106/1,767	6.00	0.95(0.77-1.17)	1.02(0.82-1.28)	Third	104/1,669	6.23	1.11(0.89-1.37)	1.19(0.95-1.5)
Between 7 and 8 years (n=12,237)					Between 7 and 8 years (n=11,512)				
First	389/5,871	6.63	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	304/5,479	5.55	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	325/4,633	7.01	1.06(0.92-1.22)	1.10(0.94-1.27)	Second	281/4,437	6.33	1.14(0.98-1.34)	1.21(1.02-1.42)
Third	102/1,733	5.89	0.89(0.72-1.10)	0.93(0.74-1.16)	Third	96/1,596	6.02	1.08(0.87-1.35)	1.17(0.92-1.49)
Between 8 and 9 years (n=12,061)					Between 8 and 9 years (n=11,395)				
First	368/5,810	6.33	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	302/5,395	5.60	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	294/4,562	6.44	1.02(0.88-1.18)	1.07(0.91-1.25)	Second	280/4,387	6.38	1.14(0.97-1.33)	1.14(0.96-1.34)
Third	109/1,689	6.45	1.02(0.83-1.25)	1.10(0.88-1.38)	Third	102/1,613	6.32	1.13(0.91-1.40)	1.14(0.91-1.45)

CI, confidence interval; RR, risk ratio.

* Adjusted for child factors(sex, singleton or multiple birth, term or preterm birth), parental factors(maternal age at delivery, maternal smoking status, maternal educational attainment, and paternal educational attainment), and residential place of living.

Figure 3.

Adjusted* RRs for the association between different birth order and atopic dermatitis stratified by sex.

A male

* Adjusted for child factors (sex, singleton or multiple birth, term or preterm birth), parental factors (maternal age at delivery, maternal smoking status, maternal educational attainment, and paternal educational attainment), and residential place of living.

* p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001, the p-values compared to the first is provided from a test of multiplicative interaction.

Table 10.

Crude and adjusted* RRs for the association between different birth order and bronchial asthma stratified by day care attendance at the age of 1.5 years.

non-daycare attendance	Ncase/N	% of cases	Crude RRs (95% CI)	Adjusted* RRs (95% CI)	daycare attendance	Ncase/N	% of cases	Crude RRs (95% CI)	Adjusted* RRs (95% CI)
Between 6 and 18 months (n=22,972)					Between 6 and 18 months (n=9,054)				
First	134/10,970	1.22	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	217/4,085	5.31	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	293/8,676	3.38	2.76(2.26-3.39)	3.03(2.46-3.74)	Second	222/3,432	6.47	1.22(1.02-1.46)	1.24(1.02-1.50)
Third	137/3,326	4.12	3.37(2.67-4.27)	4.01(3.11-5.16)	Third	136/1,537	8.85	1.67(1.36-2.05)	1.61(1.28-2.03)
Between 18 and 30 months (n=21,103)					Between 18 and 30 months (n=8,126)				
First	294/10,046	2.93	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	274/3,701	7.40	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	419/8,023	5.22	1.78(1.54-2.07)	1.85(1.59-2.16)	Second	251/3,078	8.15	1.10(0.93-1.3)	1.13(0.95-1.34)
Third	167/3,034	5.50	1.88(1.56-2.26)	2.03(1.67-2.48)	Third	108/1,347	8.02	1.08(0.87-1.34)	1.06(0.84-1.35)
Between 30 and 42 months (n=19,636)					Between 30 and 42 months (n=7,533)				
First	433/9,310	4.65	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	244/3,457	7.06	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	461/7,534	6.12	1.32(1.16-1.49)	1.38(1.21-1.57)	Second	230/2,853	8.06	1.14(0.96-1.36)	1.13(0.94-1.35)
Third	182/2,792	6.52	1.4(1.18-1.66)	1.48(1.24-1.78)	Third	98/1,223	8.01	1.14(0.91-1.42)	1.12(0.87-1.43)
Between 42 and 54 months (n=18,672)					Between 42 and 54 months (n=7,030)				
First	639/8,952	7.14	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	197/3,235	6.09	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	496/7,120	6.97	0.98(0.87-1.09)	0.98(0.87-1.10)	Second	190/2,686	7.07	1.16(0.96-1.41)	1.17(0.95-1.43)
Third	189/2,600	7.27	1.02(0.87-1.19)	1.02(0.86-1.20)	Third	82/1,109	7.39	1.21(0.95-1.56)	1.20(0.91-1.57)
Between 54 and 66 months (n=18,633)					Between 54 and 66 months (n=7,041)				
First	681/8,958	7.60	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	193/3,258	5.92	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	475/7,080	6.71	0.88(0.79-0.99)	0.89(0.79-1.00)	Second	188/2,670	7.04	1.19(0.98-1.44)	1.15(0.94-1.41)
Third	171/2,595	6.59	0.87(0.74-1.02)	0.85(0.72-1.01)	Third	79/1,113	7.10	1.20(0.93-1.54)	1.11(0.84-1.45)
Between 66 months and 7years (n=17,266)					Between 66 months and 7years (n=6,497)				
First	478/8,329	5.74	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	139/3,033	4.58	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	355/6,625	5.36	0.93(0.82-1.07)	0.94(0.82-1.08)	Second	145/2,453	5.91	1.29(1.03-1.62)	1.30(1.02-1.65)
Third	111/2,312	4.80	0.84(0.68-1.02)	0.82(0.66-1.01)	Third	48/1,011	4.75	1.04(0.75-1.43)	1.01(0.71-1.42)
Between 7 and 8 years (n=16,850)					Between 7 and 8 years (n=6,253)				
First	409/8,143	5.02	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	116/2,929	3.96	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	269/6,448	4.17	0.83(0.71-0.97)	0.83(0.72-0.97)	Second	121/2,367	5.11	1.29(1.01-1.66)	1.33(1.03-1.73)
Third	82/2,259	3.63	0.72(0.57-0.91)	0.68(0.53-0.87)	Third	36/957	3.76	0.95(0.66-1.37)	0.93(0.63-1.37)
Between 8 and 9 years (n=16,627)					Between 8 and 9 years (n=6,224)				
First	369/8,031	4.59	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	109/2,905	3.75	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	285/6,354	4.49	0.98(0.84-1.14)	0.98(0.84-1.14)	Second	111/2,362	4.70	1.25(0.97-1.62)	1.39(1.06-1.83)
Third	80/2,242	3.57	0.78(0.61-0.98)	0.73(0.57-0.94)	Third	34/957	3.55	0.95(0.65-1.38)	1.04(0.70-1.57)

CI, confidence interval; RR, risk ratio.

* Adjusted for child factors(sex, singleton or multiple birth, term or preterm birth), parental factors(maternal age at delivery, maternal smoking status, maternal educational attainment, and paternal educational attainment), and residential place of living.

Figure 4.

Adjusted* RRs for the association between different birth order and bronchial asthma stratified by day care attendance at the age of 1.5 years.

A non-day care attendance

* Adjusted for child factors (sex, singleton or multiple birth, term or preterm birth), parental factors (maternal age at delivery, maternal smoking status, maternal educational attainment, and paternal educational attainment), and residential place of living.

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, the p-values compared to the first is provided from a test of multiplicative interaction.

Table 11.

Crude and adjusted* RRs for the association between different birth order and food allergy stratified by day care attendance at the age of 1.5 years.

non-daycare attendance	Ncase/N	% of cases	Crude RRs (95% CI)	Adjusted* RRs (95% CI)	daycare attendance	Ncase/N	% of cases	Crude RRs (95% CI)	Adjusted* RRs (95% CI)
Between 6 and 18 months (n=22,972)					Between 6 and 18 months (n=9,054)				
First	736/10,970	6.71	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	311/4,085	7.61	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	401/8,676	4.62	0.69(0.61-0.78)	0.69(0.61-0.77)	Second	244/3,432	7.11	0.93(0.79-1.10)	0.94(0.79-1.11)
Third	113/3,326	3.40	0.51(0.42-0.61)	0.54(0.44-0.66)	Third	74/1,537	4.81	0.63(0.49-0.81)	0.64(0.49-0.84)
Between 18 and 30 months (n=21,103)					Between 18 and 30 months (n=8,126)				
First	396/10,046	3.94	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	185/3,701	5.00	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	246/8,023	3.07	0.78(0.67-0.91)	0.78(0.67-0.92)	Second	143/3,078	4.65	0.93(0.75-1.15)	0.95(0.76-1.19)
Third	83/3,034	2.74	0.69(0.55-0.88)	0.75(0.59-0.96)	Third	43/1,347	3.19	0.64(0.46-0.88)	0.72(0.51-1.02)
Between 30 and 42 months (n=19,636)					Between 30 and 42 months (n=7,533)				
First	291/9,310	3.13	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	101/3,457	2.92	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	166/7,534	2.20	0.70(0.58-0.85)	0.71(0.58-0.86)	Second	101/2,853	3.54	1.21(0.92-1.59)	1.25(0.94-1.67)
Third	55/2,792	1.97	0.63(0.47-0.84)	0.66(0.49-0.89)	Third	24/1,223	1.96	0.67(0.43-1.04)	0.65(0.40-1.05)
Between 42 and 54 months (n=18,672)					Between 42 and 54 months (n=7,030)				
First	208/8,952	2.32	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	68/3,235	2.10	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	140/7,120	1.97	0.85(0.68-1.05)	0.85(0.68-1.05)	Second	61/2,686	2.27	1.08(0.77-1.52)	1.1(0.77-1.59)
Third	38/2,600	1.46	0.63(0.45-0.89)	0.64(0.45-0.92)	Third	16/1,109	1.44	0.69(0.4-1.18)	0.78(0.44-1.39)
Between 54 and 66 months (n=18,633)					Between 54 and 66 months (n=7,041)				
First	145/8,958	1.62	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	46/3,258	1.41	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	96/7,080	1.36	0.84(0.65-1.08)	0.81(0.62-1.05)	Second	40/2,670	1.50	1.06(0.7-1.62)	1.01(0.65-1.56)
Third	25/2,595	0.96	0.60(0.39-0.91)	0.60(0.39-0.93)	Third	13/1,113	1.17	0.83(0.45-1.53)	0.79(0.41-1.5)
Between 66 months and 7years (n=17,266)					Between 66 months and 7years (n=6,497)				
First	160/8,329	1.92	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	52/3,033	1.71	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	120/6,625	1.81	0.94(0.75-1.19)	0.90(0.71-1.14)	Second	47/2,453	1.92	1.12(0.76-1.65)	1.06(0.7-1.58)
Third	30/2,312	1.30	0.68(0.46-0.99)	0.67(0.45-1.00)	Third	12/1,011	1.19	0.69(0.37-1.29)	0.60(0.31-1.18)
Between 7 and 8 years (n=16,850)					Between 7 and 8 years (n=6,253)				
First	125/8,143	1.54	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	40/2,929	1.37	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	99/6,448	1.54	1.00(0.77-1.30)	0.92(0.7-1.20)	Second	30/2,367	1.27	0.93(0.58-1.49)	0.86(0.53-1.4)
Third	16/2,259	0.71	0.46(0.27-0.77)	0.44(0.26-0.74)	Third	12/957	1.25	0.92(0.48-1.74)	0.83(0.42-1.64)
Between 8 and 9 years (n=16,627)					Between 8 and 9 years (n=6,224)				
First	128/8,031	1.59	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	39/2,905	1.34	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	89/6,354	1.40	0.88(0.67-1.15)	0.83(0.63-1.10)	Second	38/2,362	1.61	1.20(0.77-1.87)	1.21(0.77-1.92)
Third	21/2,242	0.94	0.59(0.37-0.93)	0.56(0.35-0.90)	Third	6/957	0.63	0.47(0.20-1.10)	0.82(0.15-1.05)

CI, confidence interval; RR, risk ratio.

* Adjusted for child factors(sex, singleton or multiple birth, term or preterm birth), parental factors(maternal age at delivery, maternal smoking status, maternal educational attainment, and paternal educational attainment), and residential place of living.

Figure 5.

Adjusted* RRs for the association between different birth order and food allergy stratified by day care attendance at the age of 1.5 years.

A non-day care attendance

* Adjusted for child factors (sex, singleton or multiple birth, term or preterm birth), parental factors (maternal age at delivery, maternal smoking status, maternal educational attainment, and paternal educational attainment), and residential place of living.

* p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001, the p-values compared to the first is provided from a test of multiplicative interaction.

Table 12.

Crude and adjusted* RRs for the association between different birth order and atopic dermatitis stratified by day care attendance at the age of 1.5 years.

non-daycare attendance	Ncase/N	% of cases	Crude RRs (95% CI)	Adjusted* RRs (95% CI)	daycare attendance	Ncase/N	% of cases	Crude RRs (95% CI)	Adjusted* RRs (95% CI)
Between 6 and 18 months (n=22,972)					Between 6 and 18 months (n=9,054)				
First	372/10,970	3.39	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	183/4,085	4.48	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	305/8,676	3.52	1.04(0.89-1.20)	1.10(0.94-1.28)	Second	162/3,432	4.72	1.05(0.86-1.30)	1.08(0.87-1.34)
Third	127/3,326	3.82	1.13(0.92-1.37)	1.26(1.02-1.55)	Third	59/1,537	3.84	0.86(0.64-1.14)	0.91(0.67-1.25)
Between 18 and 30 months (n=21,103)					Between 18 and 30 months (n=8,126)				
First	373/10,046	3.71	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	194/3,701	5.24	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	357/8,023	4.45	1.20(1.04-1.38)	1.22(1.06-1.41)	Second	178/3,078	5.78	1.10(0.91-1.34)	1.16(0.94-1.43)
Third	144/3,034	4.75	1.28(1.06-1.54)	1.35(1.10-1.64)	Third	87/1,347	6.46	1.23(0.96-1.57)	1.33(1.01-1.75)
Between 30 and 42 months (n=19,636)					Between 30 and 42 months (n=7,533)				
First	396/9,310	4.25	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	193/3,457	5.58	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	387/7,534	5.14	1.21(1.05-1.38)	1.27(1.10-1.46)	Second	175/2,853	6.13	1.10(0.90-1.34)	1.12(0.91-1.37)
Third	143/2,792	5.12	1.20(1.00-1.45)	1.33(1.09-1.62)	Third	93/1,223	7.60	1.36(1.07-1.73)	1.44(1.10-1.87)
Between 42 and 54 months (n=18,672)					Between 42 and 54 months (n=7,030)				
First	454/8,952	5.07	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	201/3,235	6.21	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	439/7,120	6.17	1.22(1.07-1.38)	1.24(1.09-1.42)	Second	165/2,686	6.14	0.99(0.81-1.21)	1.02(0.83-1.26)
Third	144/2,600	5.54	1.09(0.91-1.31)	1.16(0.96-1.41)	Third	84/1,109	7.57	1.22(0.95-1.56)	1.33(1.01-1.74)
Between 54 and 66 months (n=18,633)					Between 54 and 66 months (n=7,041)				
First	419/8,958	4.68	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	174/3,258	5.34	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	381/7,080	5.38	1.15(1.01-1.32)	1.18(1.02-1.35)	Second	159/2,670	5.96	1.12(0.9-1.37)	1.19(0.95-1.47)
Third	143/2,595	5.51	1.18(0.98-1.42)	1.27(1.04-1.54)	Third	73/1,113	6.56	1.23(0.94-1.6)	1.30(0.97-1.73)
Between 66 months and 7years (n=17,266)					Between 66 months and 7years (n=6,497)				
First	465/8,329	5.58	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	210/3,033	6.92	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	412/6,625	6.22	1.11(0.98-1.27)	1.14(1.00-1.3)	Second	170/2,453	6.93	1.00(0.82-1.22)	1.2(0.87-1.30)
Third	125/2,312	5.41	0.97(0.80-1.17)	1.04(0.85-1.27)	Third	78/1,011	7.72	1.11(0.87-1.43)	1.2(0.92-1.58)
Between 7 and 8 years (n=16,850)					Between 7 and 8 years (n=6,253)				
First	472/8,143	5.80	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	201/2,929	6.86	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	404/6,448	6.27	1.08(0.95-1.23)	1.10(0.97-1.26)	Second	186/2,367	7.86	1.15(0.95-1.39)	1.23(1.01-1.51)
Third	127/2,259	5.62	0.97(0.80-1.17)	1.02(0.83-1.24)	Third	63/9,57	6.58	0.96(0.73-1.26)	1.04(0.78-1.40)
Between 8 and 9 years (n=16,627)					Between 8 and 9 years (n=6,224)				
First	469/8,031	5.84	1(ref.)	1(ref.)	First	180/2,905	6.20	1(ref.)	1(ref.)
Second	396/6,354	6.23	1.07(0.94-1.21)	1.09(0.95-1.24)	Second	159/2,362	6.73	1.09(0.88-1.34)	1.13(0.91-1.4)
Third	133/2,242	5.93	1.02(0.84-1.22)	1.06(0.87-1.29)	Third	73/957	7.63	1.23(0.95-1.60)	1.25(0.94-1.67)

CI, confidence interval; RR, risk ratio.

* Adjusted for child factors(sex, singleton or multiple birth, term or preterm birth), parental factors(maternal age at delivery, maternal smoking status, maternal educational attainment, and paternal educational attainment), and residential place of living.

Figure 6.

Adjusted* RRs for the association between different birth order and atopic dermatitis stratified by day care attendance at the age of 1.5 years.

A non-day care attendance

B day care attendance

* Adjusted for child factors (sex, singleton or multiple birth, term or preterm birth), parental factors (maternal age at delivery, maternal smoking status, maternal educational attainment, and paternal educational attainment), and residential place of living.

* p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001, the p-values compared to the first is provided from a test of multiplicative interaction.

Figure 7.

Interaction between birth order and daycare attendance on bronchial asthma prevalence by age.

* Adjusted for child factors (sex, singleton or multiple birth, term or preterm birth), parental factors (maternal age at delivery, maternal smoking status, maternal educational attainment, and paternal educational attainment), and residential place of living.

* $p < 0.05$, the p-values compared to the first is provided from a test of multiplicative interaction.

Figure 8.

Interaction between birth order and daycare attendance on bronchial asthma prevalence by age.

* Adjusted for child factors (sex, singleton or multiple birth, term or preterm birth), parental factors (maternal age at delivery, maternal smoking status, maternal educational attainment, and paternal educational attainment), and residential place of living.

* $p < 0.05$, the p-values compared to the first is provided from a test of multiplicative interaction.

Figure 9.

Interaction between birth order and daycare attendance on bronchial asthma prevalence by age.

* Adjusted for child factors (sex, singleton or multiple birth, term or preterm birth), parental factors (maternal age at delivery, maternal smoking status, maternal educational attainment, and paternal educational attainment), and residential place of living.

* $p < 0.05$, the p-values compared to the first is provided from a test of multiplicative interaction.